

AN ADAPTIVE BASE ISOLATOR FOR CLT STRUCTURES USING FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Cross Laminated timber (CLT) can build mid-rise structures in overpopulated urban area to solve the residential problem and reduce drastic carbon emission. This kind of material can probably replace the conventional reinforced concrete and steel structures due to its sufficient strength, prefabricated members and short construction time. Up to date, there are two 18-story CLT buildings in Canada and Europe. Yet there are only two CLT buildings in Taiwan. The major concern is the seismic resistance of mass timber structures is not fully investigated.

This study tries to use fiber reinforced elastomeric isolator made of hybrid carbon/Kevlar fabric, layered rubber sheet and adaptive core material as sliding layer to design and fabricate a base isolator with adjustable damping ratios. Since the lead core in the LRB (lead rubber bearing) emits poisonous substance during excessive lateral motion under strong earthquake. The environmentally friendly materials for the sliding core can replace the lead core and increase the hysteresis loop area to achieve an adjustable equivalent damping ratio for this kind of innovative adaptive isolator.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Cross Laminated timber (CLT) had been widely used in the residential and commercial buildings in Europe and America. CLT is a kind of engineered ply wood. Commonly, each ply of the CLT composed of spruce or fir board. Each layer is orthogonal to adjacent layer to form an orthogonal composite laminate which is equivalent to a cross ply and can sustain loads in both directions. The CLT Panels are prefabricated based on the project design and arrive at the job site with windows and doors pre-cut. Up to date the 18 story Brock Commons at University of British Columbia Canada is the highest CLT building in the world. There are only two CLT buildings in Taiwan. Although there are several researchers reported that the low rise CLT building (up to 8 stories) can sustain the strong ground motion without visible damage of the main CLT structure, adoption of inexpensive and light-weight base isolator in mid-rise CLT building is still rare. This study proposes an innovative fiber reinforced elastomeric isolator (FREI) made of hybrid carbon/Kevlar fabric and layered rubber to replace a conventional layered steel rubber seismic isolator. Optimal volume fraction of hybrid carbon/Kevlar fabric, adhesives, curing pressure, and curing temperature are evaluated through a series of designed tests. After the curing of FREI, the specimen is cut into the desired size and its vertical stiffness, horizontal stiffness, and equivalent damping ratio are characterized by the vertical loading, and biaxial loading tests. In order to improve its damping characteristic, the central core of this elastomer isolator is replaced by sliding plates to absorb vibration energy. The horizontal, vertical stiffness and damping ratio can be adjusted through the thickness, mechanical properties and volume fraction of various sliding materials.

2 DESIGN OF ADAPTIVE RUBBER/COMPOSITE BEARINGS

The lead core rubber bearings (LRB) have been widely used in earthquake base isolation due to their low horizontal stiffness and large energy dissipation capacity during excessive lateral displacements. However, under extreme displacement, the temperature inside the lead core rises abruptly which results in lessening the yield strength of the lead material, the degradation of stiffness, and even emits some poisonous material. Therefore, it is necessary to use some alternative core materials that can sustain large lateral displacement having adequate vertical stiffness and adjustable damping. Figure 1 shows the design configuration of an adaptive rubber bearing isolator. The top and

bottom end plates are steel plates to be respectively connected to the upper structure and lower foundation. The original rubber/steel layered structure is replaced by the rubber/composite laminate subsets. The sliding plate has a high compressive strength and compressive modulus which can provide sufficient vertical stiffness. For easy sliding, there is no bounding agent between the sliding plate and interface shim. The layer number and thickness of the sliding plates and shims can be adjusted according to seismic isolation requirement. A special curing adhesive is needed to bound the rubber and fiber composite laminated when co-cure process is not adopted. Fig. 2 demonstrates the different carbon/Kevlar yarn volume fraction in this study.

Figure 1: Configuration of an adaptive rubber/composite bearing

Figure 2: Types of hybrid Carbon/Kevlar fabrics

The composite laminates are made of hybrid Carbon/Kevlar fabric from Formosa Plastic Group, Taiwan. The carbon roving TC360 has a tensile strength of 4890 MPa, and tensile modulus of 250 GPa, respectively. The uni-directional (UD) carbon fabric when cured with epoxy/resin has the following mechanical properties: $E_1 = 117.29$ GPa, $E_2 = E_3 = 7.44$ GPa, $G_{12} = 3.77$ GPa and $\nu_{12} = 0.1946$, respectively. A $[0_2/90_4/0_4/90_4/0_2]_s$ cross-ply laminated was fabricated using 16 layer of UD carbon fabrics. The measured effective moduli are $E_x = E_y = 56.87$ GPa, which is close to the effective modulus using 3-D effective moduli as $E_x = E_y = 62.48$ GPa, $G_{xy} = 3.77$ GPa, and $G_{xz} = G_{yz} = 3.056$ GPa. For the measurement of the relation of horizontal shear force and displacement, the following double lap shear set-up is adopted to evaluate the hysteresis loop of lateral displacement force of the rubber/steel and rubber/composite laminate system.

Figure 3: Double lap shear set-up for rubber/steel and rubber/composite laminate system.

The height of rubber is 10mm, with a width of 25mm and bonding length of 60 mm, while the steel plates or the carbon composite laminates have a thickness of 6 mm.

2.1 Effective stiffness and equivalent damping ratio of a typical rubber bearing

For a rubber bearing isolator, the effective horizontal stiffness is defined as

$$K_{eff} = \frac{F_i^+ - F_i^-}{2\Delta_i} \quad (1)$$

where F_i^+ and F_i^- are, the maximum and minimum shear forces in a hysteresis loop, respectively. The Δ_i is the average of the maximum positive and negative horizontal displacements. The equivalent damping ξ_e^i for the i^{th} loop can be expressed as

$$\xi_e^i = \frac{E_d^i}{2\pi k_{eff}^i \Delta_i^2} \quad (2)$$

where E_d^i is the area of hysteresis loop of an isolation unit. The effective shear modulus G_{eff} can be obtained as

$$G_{eff} = \frac{K_{eff} H_r}{A} \quad (3)$$

where H_r and A are height and area of a shear unit; $H_r = 10\text{mm}$, and $A = 1250 \text{ mm}^2$ in a typical layer of a rubber bearing in this study.

Figures 4 and 5 show the effective stiffness, shear modulus and equivalent damping ratio of a rubber/steel and rubber/carbon composite isolator under different displacements, respectively. It reveals that under the same displacement, the rubber/steel isolation unit has lower effective stiffness and higher equivalent damping ratio than the rubber/carbon composite unit. The decrease in the equivalent damping ratio of rubber/carbon composite unit is less than 10% in most cases.

Figure 4: Horizontal shear test of steel/rubber

Figure 5: Horizontal shear test of carbon fabric/rubber

2.2 Effective stiffness and equivalent damping ratio of entire adaptive rubber bearing

Referring to refer to Figures 6 and 7, the effective stiffness K_{eff} of the ARB can be expressed as [2]

$$K_{eff} = K_{eff}^{rb} + \frac{K_{eff}^{rb}}{u} \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq n}}^N \frac{a_i W \mu_i}{k_{eff}^{ri}} \quad (4)$$

Where

$$\frac{1}{K_{eff}^{rb}} = \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq n}}^N \frac{1}{k_{eff}^{ri}} = \frac{1}{k_{eff}^{r1}} + \frac{1}{k_{eff}^{r2}} + \frac{1}{k_{eff}^{r3}} + \dots + \frac{1}{k_{eff}^{rn-1}} + \frac{1}{k_{eff}^{rn+1}} \dots + \frac{1}{k_{eff}^{rN}} \quad (5)$$

and k_{eff}^{ri} represents the effective stiffness of rubber material in the i^{th} layer, as shown in Figure 6; a_i is the percentage of the total vertical load sustained by the sliding plates in the i^{th} layer; μ_i denotes the friction coefficients of sliding interfaces in the i^{th} layer; N is the total number of rubber layers; n is the number of the layer which is not active in sliding motion; and u is the total displacement of the isolator.

With reference to Figures 6 and 7, the equivalent damping ratio ξ_e of the ARB is given by [2]

$$\xi_e = \frac{1}{2\pi K_{eff} u^2} \left\{ \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq n}}^N \frac{2\pi \xi_{ri}}{k_{eff}^{ri}} \left[\left(K_{eff}^{rb} u + K_{eff}^{rb} \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq n}}^N \frac{a_i W \mu_i}{k_{eff}^{ri}} \right) - a_i W \mu_i \right]^2 \right\} + \frac{1}{2\pi K_{eff} u^2} \left\{ \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq n}}^N \frac{4\mu_i a_i W}{k_{eff}^{ri}} \left[\left(K_{eff}^{rb} u + K_{eff}^{rb} \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq n}}^N \frac{a_i W \mu_i}{k_{eff}^{ri}} \right) - a_i W \mu_i \right] \right\} \quad (6)$$

In the case of identical material properties including those of rubber and sliding plates in all layers, we have $a=a_i$ and $\mu=\mu_i$ to yield the effective stiffness of the entire isolator as follows: [2]

$$K_{eff} = K_{eff}^{rb} + \frac{aW\mu}{u} \quad (7)$$

As a special case, when the same material properties are used in all layers, then the equivalent damping ratio of the entire isolator can be obtained as: [2]

$$\xi_e = \frac{\xi_e^{rb}}{1 + \frac{aW\mu}{K_{eff}^{rb}u}} + \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{K_{eff}^{rb}u}{aW\mu}} \quad (8)$$

Figure 6: Hysteresis loop of a single layer of rubber material.

Figure 7: Hysteresis loop of sliding core in a single layer.

3 EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL RESULTS OF FULL SCALE ARB/STEEL BEARINGS

In this section, test results of full-scale adaptive rubber/steel bearing specimens are presented to validate the concept of the ARB/steel proposed in this study [2]. Figure 8 shows the details of a full-scale ARB/steel. The bearing was 700 mm in diameter, and had a 5-mm cover, 16 layers of rubber of 4 mm in thickness in each layer, a sliding core of 300 mm in diameter, and 15 shim plates of 4 mm each in thickness. Three sliding plates were implemented in each layer of 4 mm in thickness that was the same the thickness as the rubber layer. These sliding plates were located between two adjacent shim plates to form two major sliding interfaces and were used to smooth the sliding motion of the sliding interfaces without making noise. It is possible and practical to have more than two sliding interfaces in a single layer by adopting thinner sliding plates to further reduce displacement and heat at each sliding interface by adding sliding plates. It may also be possible to design the contact surface between the shim and sliding plates as a sliding interface for additional functionality.

Generally, the sliding displacement distributed at each sliding interface is much smaller than its diameter. The choice of materials for sliding plates is dependent on their vertical stiffness, friction coefficient, strength, wear resistance, specific heat, and melting temperature. Figure 9 shows the test set-up for the bearings located at the Taoyuan Laboratory of CECI Nova Technology Co., Ltd., Taiwan. The capacity of the testing machine is 9810kN force in the vertical direction, 981kN force in the horizontal direction and a displacement of 225mm in the horizontal direction. Figure 10 shows the photo of the full-scale ARB specimen and the arrangement of the measurement instruments.

Figure 8: Details of full-scale ARB Specimen.

Figure 9: Photo of testing machine.

Figure 10: Photo of ARB/steel specimen before testing.

Figure 11: Hysteresis loops at strain of 100% under pressure of 10MPa.

Figures 11-15 show the hysteresis loops of the displacements vs. forces in the horizontal direction while the full-scale specimen was subjected to 100%, 150%, 200% and 250% of shear strains in rubber, and under a vertical load of 3740 kN to produce a vertical pressure of 10MPa. The test results shown in Figures 11-15 were completed without recess. It has been proven from these figures by observing the enclosed areas of displacements vs. forces that the full-scale ARB/steel specimen possesses quite stable and excellent behavior of absorbing energy induced by cyclic loadings without significant decline in energy absorption capacity, and that the sliding plates play a major role in absorbing vibration energy. In addition, as we predicted in the mathematical formulations, the frictional force contributed by the sliding core can provide considerable damping to the isolator by viewing the enclosed area derived from the force-displacement loops. In contrast, the rubber material provides little damping to the device. As shown in Figure 15, a very small change in stiffness and damping ratios within ten cycles of reversal loadings occurred because the sliding mechanism in the sliding core of the ARB/steel was uniformly distributed on all sliding surfaces between sliding plates to lessen the temperature effect.

Figure 12: Hysteresis loops at strain of 150% under pressure of 10MPa.

Figure 13: Hysteresis loops at strain of 200% under pressure of 10MPa.

Figure 14: Hysteresis loops at strain of 250% under pressure of 10MPa.

Figure 15: Ten cycles of hysteresis loops at strain of 200% and 10MPa pressure.

Figures 16 and 17 respectively present the effective stiffness and equivalent damping ratio of the ARB specimen. Both the effective stiffness and equivalent damping ratio decrease with an increase of the shear strain as we expected from the mathematical formulation provided in the last section. The damping ratio is 55.99% at the shear strain of 50%, 49.37% at the shear strain of 100% and 35.09% at the shear strain of 250%. It has been surely proven from these test results that the ARB isolator would provide great damping to absorb seismic energy and to reduce the isolator displacement during an earthquake.

Figure 16: Effective stiffness at various levels of strains under pressure of 10MPa.

Figure 17: Damping ratio at various levels of strains under pressure of 10MPa.

Figures 18 and 19 respectively show the hysteresis loops at the strains of 300% and 350% that is a displacement of 224mm while the bearing sustained a vertical load of 7479kN to produce a vertical pressure of 20MPa. The damping ratios for these two cases were 34.80% and 30.68%, respectively. From the tested results presented in this section, it is concluded that the ARB isolator possesses great damping ratios from small to large shear strains. Figures 20 and 21 show the front and side views of the full-scale ARB specimen after testing, respectively. These pictures show that there was no sign of damage to the tested ARB/steel specimen even after a large number of cycling loadings and large strains thus confirming the durability of the full-scale ARB/steel isolator. In addition, the equivalent damping ratio of the ARB/steel remained extremely high at a large displacement compared to those of the LRB and high damping rubber bearing (HDRB) [4].

Figure 18: Hysteresis loops at strain of 300% under pressure of 20MPa.

Figure 19: Hysteresis loops at strain of 350% under pressure of 20MPa.

Figure 20: Front view of ARB/steel specimen after testing.

Figure 21: Side view of ARB/steel specimen after testing.

Figures 22 and 23 respectively present the comparison of the analytical and experimental results of the effective stiffness and equivalent damping ratio of the ARB/steel. These comparisons show that a good agreement between analytical and experimental results has been obtained.

Figure 22. Effective stiffness at various levels of strains under pressure of 10MPa

Figure 23. Damping ratio at various levels of strains under pressure of 10MPa

4 CONCLUSIONS

New seismic isolators named the adaptive rubber/steel/composite bearings have been proposed in this study. The following conclusions can be drawn after the ARB tests and their comparisons with analytical results:

1. The ARB isolator uses environmentally friendly materials.
2. The ARB isolator possesses stable mechanical behavior.
3. The ARB isolator provides extremely high damping by means of a sliding mechanism in the sliding core.
4. The decrease in damping ratio of the proposed ARB device with an increased displacement is not significant.
5. The proposed rubber bearing is durable to sustain many reversal loadings.
6. The analytical result has a good agreements with experimental result.

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